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Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials II

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for production engineers, textile engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of textile fibre processing and yarn manufacturing. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Textile Raw Materials - II

- Q. What is man made fibre & features of man made fibre
- Q. Classification of man made fibre
- Q. Different forms of man made fibre
- Q. What are the basic fibre forming properties required for fibre forming polymers.
- Q. Briefly describe about chemical and physical modification of man made fibre.
- Q. How can you modify the spinning solution of MMF
- Q. What is your understanding about spinneret used for producing man made fibre
- Q. State the cleaning process of spinneret.
- Q. Write down the basic flow chart of spinneret.

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Spinneret: A nozzle or plate provided with fine holes or slits through a fibre-forming solution or melt is extruded in fibre manufacturing is called spinneret

Fig: spinneret

Features: 01) Spinneret holes are slightly wider at the entry than the exit.

02) The denier of filament extruded through a hole does not depend upon its size, but it has some significance on the efficient extrusion depending on melt delivery speed.

Write down the basic sequence of man made fibre production

01. Manufacturing of fibre-forming polymer
02. Spinning (extrusion through spinneret)
03. stretching/drawing (improving strength and crystallinity) → Drawn filament
04. Texturing/impiling (developing material fibre properties)
05. Intermingling/interlacing (applied instead of twisting) (spot welding to protrude filament)
06. Heat setting (made dimensionally stable)

(or)

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Principles of different spinning system :

Three types of spinning process : 1) Melt 2) Wet 3) Dry

01. Melt spinning : The process of spinning by which fibre or filament is produced from melted chips (cut or break into small pieces) by extruding through spinneret.

Process : 01. The fibre forming polymer are fed into hopper which are electrically heated over melting point where crosslinking of the polymer may occur.

02. The hot molten polymer is protected from surrounding oxygen and is effected by Nitrogen, Carbon-di-oxide or steam.

03. By pumping system, polymer melt is forced to through the fine holes of spinneret.

04. After cooling and solidification, solid filaments are collected in packaged form.

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Dry spinning: In dry spinning the fibre forming polymer dissolved in a volatile solvent is introduced into a heated drying chamber where the solvent is evaporated and solid fibre is obtained through spinneret.

Filament is formed by the simple evaporation of solvent which can be enhanced by passing dry nitrogen.

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Wet spinning: In wet spinning a suitable solvent is used to prepare fibre forming solution and coagulant (স্রাবকরণ) is used in coagulating bath where solution is extruded through spinneret in contact of coagulant.

** The solution is extruded through spinneret which is immersed in a coagulation bath where cellulose is regenerated and converted into the filament.

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Differentiate among melt, dry and wet spinning

01. Principle	Def ⁿ	Def ⁿ	Def ⁿ
02. Polymer conc. & viscosity	High	Medium	Medium
03. Spg speed	2500-3000 ft/min	2500-3000 ft/min	150-300 ft/min
04. Fibres	Nylon, Polyester, Polyolefin, Polypropylene	Acetate, Triacetate, Modacrylic, Spandex, PVA, PAN and some polyacrylonitrile fibres PVA → Polyvinyl Alcohol PAN → Polyacrylonitrile	Vincelone, PVA, PAN
05. Hazard	Non toxic	Toxic	Toxic
06. Investment cost	Low	High	Low

Drawing: The process by which the yarn/fibre is elongated by passing through a series of pairs of rollers, each pair moving faster than the previous one is called drawing.

- objects:**
- To increase strength
 - To reduce elongation at break
 - To reduce creep property → unwanted
 - To increase orientation & crystallinity
 - To remove brittleness & instability of the filament

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(How can be blended rayon & acetate fibres with cotton)
Texturization: is the process by which the flat filaments are distorted to have crimps, coils or loops along their length to achieve bulk and greater absorbency.

Basic principle of Texturization:

01. To heat the yarn to plastic condition
02. To impart the required shape of filament
03. To cool it to retain the shape.

Heat setting: The process of imparting dimensional stability to fibres, yarns, fabrics or garments with successive heating and cooling in dry and moist conditions is called heat setting.

The different levels of heat setting may be defined as:

- 1) Temporary set
- 2) Semi-permanent set
- 3) Permanent

Spin finish: Spin finishes are the lubricant which provides surface lubricating, plasticizing and static protection to manmade fibre. It is applied in fluid condition just before wind up.

- Object: → To lubricate yarn → To reduce static electricity
→ To increase the cohesion (সংযুক্তি) of the yarn.
→ To plasticize the fibre.

Different types of spin finishes:

a) Lubricants: used to control the friction of the fibre.
Example: Oil, polyglycol, Ester of fatty acids

b) Plasticizers: plasticizers makes the fibre more flexible by reducing the glass transition temp. and also reduce brittleness.
Example: Dibutyl, Silicate esters, Silicate

c) Antistatic agents: are hygroscopic chemicals which can reduce coefficient (সং) of friction.
Example: Inorganic salt (such as Lithium chloride)

Ester of fatty acid (Butyl stearate)

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Define regenerated fibre with example:

The fibres which we get by regeneration from its main origin is termed as regenerated fibre. The regenerated fibres are divided into four groups:

- 1. Cellulosic fibre: Viscose rayon, Cuprammonium, Modal etc.
- 2. Cellulosic esters: Acetate, Triacetate, Fortisan, Alon
- 3. Protein fibres: Casein, Zeir, Azlon
- 4. Miscellaneous: Alginate, Rubber.

Rayon: Manmade textile fibre composed of regenerated cellulose.

1. Cellulose fibre: 1937, Federal Trade Commission (FTC) defined all fibres from cellulose and its derivatives under the term 'Rayon'.
Viscose: The name viscose was derived from the word 'viscous' which describe the liquid state of the spg. solution. Viscose is a manmade, natural polymeric cellulose which is obtained by the viscose manufacturing process:

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Cupric-Ammonium Rayon Process:

Polymer structure of viscose/cupric ammonium/ polytonic or modal

- where
- $n = 350$, cellulose unit for viscose
- $n = 450$, cellulose unit cupric ammonium
- $n = 500$, cellulose unit for polytonic or modal

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Organic Solvent based manufacturing process for Tencel/Lyocel

- Properties:
- 1) Tenacity (Dry) - 4.8-5.0 g/d
 - 2) Wet modulus - 31.0 g/d
 - 3) Good comfort
 - 4) Good lusture
 - 5) Good moisture absorbency
 - 6) Wrinkle resistance
 - 7) Good drapability
 - 8) Biodegradable
 - 9) Ecofriendly.

End uses of regenerated cellulosic fibre based fibre:

01. Tencel denim looks like cotton but being soft, smooth and exhibiting drapes. Jeans like silk.
02. Curtain, chair covering, bed covers, Beach and sports wear, under wear
03. Tinted & power transmission belting
04. Sewing Embroidery, umbrella and protective clothing
05. viscose + cotton / polyester blending.

Comparative properties of Tencel, Viscose Rayon, cotton & Polyester

Properties	Tencel	Viscose R.	Cotton	Polyester
Denier (g/d)	1.5	1.5	-	1.5
Dry Tenacity (g/d)	4.8-5.0	2.6-3.1	2.4-2.9	4.8-6.0
Dry elongation (%)	14-16	20-25	7-9	44-45
Wet Tenacity (g/d)	4.2-4.6	1.2-1.8	3.1-3.6	4.8-6.0
Wet elongation (%)	16-18	25-30	12-14	44-45
Wet modulus (5% ext)	31	60	11.5	24
Water imbibition (%)	65	90	150	3

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Cellulose esters fibre / Artificial silk

Polymer structure of Cellulose

Acetate / Triacetate:

where, D.P. $n = 130$, Acetate
 $n = 225$, Triacetate

Flow chart of Acetate Manufacturing process:

Purification (Na ₂ CO ₃ /NaOH with NaOCl washing & dried)	Vincosa Region B	Acetate
↓	1. Purze callu	1. chemical compound of cellulose.
Activation (steeping in glacial Acetic Acid) <i>→ Soak in Liquid</i>	2. Tenacity Dry: 15-24 Wet: 7-12 g/d	2. Tenacity Dry: 1.1-1.2 g/d Wet: .65-.7 m g/d
Acetylation (Acetic Acid + Acetic Anhydride + H ₂ SO ₄)	3. Elongation at Break	3.
↓	Dry: 15-20% Wet: 20-25%	Dry: 25-40% Wet: 30-45%
Hydrolysis (H ₂ O added to form Acetic Acid)	4. MR-13%	4. MR-6.5%
↓	5. DP-250-300	5. DP-130
Precipitation (Excess CH ₃ COOH is added for destroying H ₂ SO ₄ & Hence Acetate precipitated)		
↓		
Washing & Drying		
↓		
Bleaching (Acetate in Acetone containing water)		
↓		
Dope preparation (filament or staple fibre)		
↓		
Dry up		

End uses: 1) Acetate in the major product for cigarette filters. 2) Lingerie 3) ties 4) Men's underwear 5) sports wear.

Mid-term
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Understanding about Protein fibres

Generic term of protein fibre is Azlon.

01. Casein fibres: Skimmed milk
(মসুরা স্নাতকীত আধার)
02. Soyabean fibres: Soyabean (Remainings after oil extraction)
03. Aradil fibres: Peanut or ground nuts
04. Vicarza fibres: a gluten meal which is the by product in the rationing of the cotton and only synthetic protein fibre is now being produced on a commercial basis in the USA.

Polyamide fibres: Nylon 6, Nylon 6.6, Nylon 11, Nylon 6.10

amide group (-CO-NH) Nylon 7

Nylon 6: 6 amino caproic Acid / Caprolactam

Nylon 6.6: Hexa-methylene diamine and adipic acid

Nylon 11: 11-Amino undecanoic Acid

Nylon 6.10: Hexa-methylene diamine and sebacic acid

Nylon 7: Amino Heptanoic Acid

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- End uses:
01. Apparel like winter wear, swimming wear
 02. Home furnishings
 03. Fishing nets
 04. Sewing thread
 05. Tarp ropes.

Properties of Nylon 66 fibre:

01. Tenacity (4.5-5.8 g/d (dry) and 4.1-5.1 (wet))
02. Elongation %: 23-42.5 (dry) and 27-34 (wet)
03. Moisture Regain: 4-4.5%
04. Initial Modulus: 35-50 g/d
05. Abrasion resistance: Excellent

Polyamide/aramid fibre

1. Nylon 6-T
2. Nomex
3. Kevlar

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Nylon 6-T: Preparation of the Polymer:

Nylon 6-T Polymer (soluble in 96% H₂SO₄)

Fibre prep: Dry jet wet spg wet spg, solvent 96% H₂SO₄.
 Polymer concentration in dope 14.5-14.9%, temp of n

Fig: Dry jet wet spg equipment Type Tensioner

Properties:

1. High Temperature resistance (250°C)
2. M.R% - 4-5%
3. strength stable at 185°C for 5 hours.

Applications:

Nomex: (By du pont)

m-phenylene Diamine

iso phthalic Acid

Acid chloride

poly m phenylene iso phthalamide or poly m-Benzamide) i.e Nomex

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- Properties:
- 1) Temp. 265-371°C
 - 2) Tenacity 4.1 g/d (wet), 5.3 g/d (dry)
 - 3) Breaking elongation: 23-30%
 - 4) Modulus: 113-120
 - 5) Thermal & cut resistance: Higher
 - 6) Chemical resistance: Medium

- Application:
- 1) High temperature filtration
 - 2) Space suits
 - 3) Racing drivers overall
 - 4) Kitchen apron
 - 5) Gloves, protective footwear.

Poly(p-phenylene terephthalamide)
 or Poly(p-Benzamide) or Kevlar-49

Properties:	Kevlar-29	49
Temperature	Degrade at 420°C	Degrade at 500°C
Tenacity (g/d)	22	22
Tensile strength	2.7 GN/m ²	2.7 GN/m ²
Young modulus	60 GN/m ²	130 GN/m ²
Breaking elongation	4%	2-2.5%
Modulus	500 g/d	1000 g/d
Cut through resistance	Very High	Highest.

- Applications:
- 1) Bullet proof vest
 - 2) Industrial belts
 - 3) High temperature resistant filtration cloth.
 - 4) Space
 - 5) Aerospace fuel tank coating

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Polyester: Polyester means many organic salts.

Polyester fibre production:

01. Ester interchange:

02. Polycondensation reaction:

Properties:

- | | |
|---|---|
| 01. High Tenacity filament: 7-8 g/d | End uses: 01. Men's, women's & children's wear |
| 02. Normal Tenacity filament: 4.5-5.0 g/d | 02. Upholster, floor covering & Carpets |
| 03. Staple fibre tenacity: 3.5-4.0 g/d | 03. Bleeding with cotton, wool, acrylic nylon etc. |
| 04. M.R. 0-0.4 | 04. Tire cord fabrics, sail cloth, conveyor belts, paper packaging, furniture fillings & Nonwoven |
| 05. Breaking extension: 20-30% | |
| 06. Specific gravity:
Dacron: 1.38, Kodal 1.22 | |

$$\text{Specific gravity} = \frac{P_{\text{sample}}}{P_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}$$

P = Density

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Polyvinyl chloride (PVC): The chemical process for making PVC involves three steps: First, production of the monomer, vinyl chloride; then the linking of these monomers with a polymerization process and finally the blending of the polymer with additives!

Fig: Prodⁿ Process of PVC

Properties:

End uses:

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Elastomeric Fibre: 01. Spandex (Lycra is the Brand name)

02. Rubber

Properties of Spandex:

- 01) Tenacity: 55-110 g/d
- 02) Elongation at break: 500%
- 03) Moisture Regain: 16%
- 04) Specific gravity: 1.21-1.35
- 05) Elastic recovery: 100%
(at 2% extension)
- 06) Dimensional stability:
No shrinkage in water
but shrinkage in temp.

End uses:

- 01. Stretch fabrics & swim wear
- 02. Foot wear
- 03. Ladies, sports & childrens underwear and outer
- 04. To maintain the functions of garment support.

05.

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Polyolefine fibre: ① Polyethylene ② Polypropylene

Production process of Polypropylene:

End uses:

01. Ropes, twines, netting for fishing industry.
02. Carpet, sweaters & sports wear
03. Industrial filtration fabrics.
04. Packaging.

Properties	Polyethylene	Polypropylene
Tenacity (g/d)	10-80	45-80
Elongation at Break	50%	15-30%
Elastic property	Flexible	Flexible
M.R%	0%	0.1%
Specific gravity	0.92-0.96	0.90-0.91

190-95%

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Properties:

01. Tenacity for staple: 2.0-3.6 g/d (dry) and 1.7-2.4 g/d (wet)
02. Elastic recovery: 90-95% at 1% extension
03. Elongation: 25-50%
04. M.R.: 1-3%
05. Specific gravity: 1.16-1.18

End uses:

01. Knitted & woven fabrics
02. Blending with wool & cotton etc.
03. Blankets, carpets & upholstery
04. Wigs (Artificially covering hair for the head)
05. Industrial application in filtration cloth.

Flow diagram steps of modacrylic fibre:

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Mineral / Inorganic fibre : 1) Glass fibre 2) carbon fibre
 3) Ceramic

Glass fibre : Raw materials of glass fibre are silica, sand, lime-stone and modifiers like Na_2CO_3 and Borax etc which are melted with high temperature (1450°) and extruded as glass fibre of different grades. Ex : E (Electrical insulation) grade and S (High strength composite) grade etc.

Production flow : End uses : 1) ship building
 2) Biological filtration station
 3) water storage tank
 4) Sludge separation
 5) Fire proof fabrics
 6) High temperature resistant pipe & cylinder
 7) Suits for astronaut.

Properties: E-glass S-glass

Density (g/cc) cubic or specific gravity	2.54	2.54
Tenacity (g/d)	7.80	11.70
Elastic Recovery	100%	100%
MPR%	0	0
Elongation at Break (%)	1-4.8	3-5.4
Abraction resistance	Poor	Poor

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Carbon fibre: Carbon fibres are formed in gas phase reactions (explosive / high temperature reactions) by carbons remaining in a special form constituting of only carbons being linearly arranged / structured in fibre form after dehydrogenation of the -CH₂- groups from hydrocarbon material

Prodⁿ: Raw material (PAN precursor) → pre-treating / drying → Oxidation in air (200-300°C) → Pre-carbonisation (1100°C) → Carbonisation in Hydrogen (1800°C) → Graphitisation in a region (the conversion of an organic material in an inert atmosphere at temp. in excess of 1800 deg. C) → Surface treatment (Anodic salt solution) → washing with hot H₂O → Drying (air or hot roller) → Sizing (epoxy resin H₂O based) → Drying (air and hot roller contact) → Winding spools of 12 kg.

PAN → Polyacrylonitrile

Activated Carbon fibre

Acrylonitrile methacrylate and its acid based polymer carbon fibres are called activated carbon fibres. The prodⁿ steps: Thermo oxidative activation, carbonisation

Properties: (PAN Based)

① Density → 1.6674 g/cc

Modulus → 234 GPa
1 kg = 1N

Strength → 2.52

Young Modulus → 230-240 GPa

Tenacity → Higher

Thermal conductivity → Higher

Composite made from carbon fibres are five times stronger than grade 1020 steel.

Higher corrosive resistance

End uses:

- 1) Used as rocket nozzles
- 2) Air craft brakes
- 3) Golf club shafts
- 4) Parts of printers and Photocopy m/c
- 5) Drive shaft for cooling tower
- 6) Submarines
- 7) Frame of racing cars

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Bi/multicomponent fibre conjugate spg: This technology involves spg of bicomponent filaments comprising of a Nylon-66 matrix with polyester fibrils where controlled arrangements of component is done successfully.

Types:
 01. Sea Island Tech. 02. Matrix filaments 03. Sheath core

04. Side by side 05. Matrix Fibril

N.B: Separation/ splitting may be achieved by mechanical beating or chemical dissolution.

Methods of production by components fibre:

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10^{-6} , 10^{-9}

Microfibrils: Any fibre of 0.1 dtex is called microfibrils.
Range of microfibrils/filament count available in various

Fibre classification → Coarse fibre → > 7.0 dtex, conventional filament and staple (cotton, wool, polyester) → $2.4 - 7.0$ dtex, Fine filament and fine staple (silk, acrylic etc) → $1.0 - 2.4$ dtex, microfibrils $0.1 - 1.0$, super microfibrils ($0.1 - 0.3$ dtex), super ultrafine → Below 0.1 dtex

Salient features of microfibrils:

- 01. Light weight and high cover
- 02. Excellent softness and drape
- 03. High dimensional stability
- 04. Silky handle and excellent comfort
- 05. Good breathability even with high cover
- 06. Higher dye absorption rate leading to lower dye levelness
- 07. Lower dye fastness to light
- 08. Low pilling

Applications:

- 01) Skirt, jacket & light wt. knitted wear
- 02) Raincoat, sailing outfit, jogging suit
- 03) Sleeping Bag, tents and upholstery
- 04) Filter fabrics, Tea Bags

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Nanofibre: Fibre with diameter in a nanometric range
ie 50-1000nm

Properties: 1) Large specific surface area 2) High porosity
3) small pore size 4) Diameter range 50-1000nm

Tech. of Nano:

In the electrospinning process a high voltage is used to create an electrically charged stream of polymer solution or melt. A high voltage electrode is linked with the polymer solution. The solution is then spun through a capillary. Due to high voltage electric field between the tip of capillary and a grounded collector, Taylor cone is formed at the top tip of capillary producing sub micron in diameter fibres. Fibres solidify as the polymer solvents evaporates and create an interlinked fibre layer on the surface of the collector.

Applications:

1. Composites, filtration, separation membranes, Biomedicine (artificial organs, tissue engineering, blood vessels, drug delivery systems, wound dressing, breathing masks)
2. Protective clothing, solar sails, light sails and mirrors for using in space
3. Application of pesticides to plants, Nanosensor, nano electric applications as field effect transistors and ultra small antennas, Hydrogen storage tank for fuel cell.

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